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POSITIVE EFFECTS OF EDUCATIONAL MOBILE APPLICATION TO THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 11 STUDENTS IN ST. GREGORY COLLEGE OF VALENZUELA

A Thesis
Presented to the Faculty of the
Senior High School Department

In Partial Fulfillment
Of the Requirements for the Track
Science Technology Engineering Mathematics

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to know the positive effects and the factors affecting the academic performance of Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela using educational mobile applications or (EMA). This study aimed to create an awareness on Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela upon using Educational Mobile Applications (EMA) which helps them in terms of studying. This study made used quantitative research, with the research instrument of gathering data are survey questionnaire and interview for the validation. The researchers conducted an interview to the five (5) Senior High School Teachers for the validation and survey questionnaires for the students in Grade 11 composed of fifty (50) from St. Gregory College of Valenzuela. The researchers analyzed the data using statistical treatment and table for the tally, to identify the effects of educational mobile applications to the academic performance of Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela. The findings show that the most positive effect of EMA is, it is the Easier way to gather data and Information and “New studying method” agreed by the students, that it is one of the best factors that affects their academic performance by using the EMA. In addition there are four limited EMA introduce by the researchers and Google is the most used EMA by the Grade 11 students from St. Gregory College of Valenzuela.

Keywords: Applications, EMA, E-Learning, E-Teaching and M-Learning.

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Chapter I

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

Education is the act of acquiring knowledge to develop the powers of reasoning in order to have a mature and intellectual life. It is also about having improvement and better life. There are types and procedures of acquiring knowledge. Learnings can be based on academic text and other learning sources. Education nowadays can be online and technological. Using educational application can improve someone's matter of learning by which the researcher want to know the effectiveness of having the educational applications in formal education.

In addition, Heick (2018) he defined mobile learning as gaining knowledge through digital devices like smartphones, tablets, and other technological gadgets. Mobile technology makes student's life easier, the students do not have to rent a computer anymore, or go to big libraries just to look for the answers they need. But, some educational application can be installed in mobile devices which can be used for easier understanding and can lead to self-studying. Also mobile application can be their reference without using internet because some educational applications can be used offline.

Addition to the ideas of the researchers, the motto "learn anytime and anywhere" is literally happening in our modern society, referring to the students who have

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their own screen as (Sharples, Taylor & Vavoula, 2007) state that mobile learning, comes from a handleable devices which aims to create a relationship between the students and their digital devices with an Internet access to get information.

Langeveld (2013), states that education is also an interaction of human beings in relation to progress of learning. In addition, education can be in various processes of learning depending on the mental stability of a human being.

By means of this study, the researchers aim to conduct a survey on how mobile applications affect the academic performance of Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela.

Theoretical Framework

Mobile Learning Theory

Sharples, Taylor and Vavoula (2007), states that mobile learning is essential when it comes to thinking of education. Educational mobile application theory explains how educational mobile application can affect the students day by day in school and outside the school. Having the mobile phones in every place can improve learning of a student in the way that students can study every time and everywhere.

Zafirakou (2018), states that there should not any hindrances for a student to access higher quality learning. In order to have higher education, one must formulate improvements using best ways and strategies. Also as Dewey (2013) said, education

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is a process of experience, developing the best basic experience of studying like having educational applications can be a good way of learning experience. In addition, as Zafirakou (2018) and Dewey (2013), ideas collide, educational application may help students to have great learning experience.

These theories will be used in the current study, given the importance of educational mobile application to help students know the effects of educational application in academic needs and academic performance. This theory aims to prove and support the study of how we need higher technologies in learning areas.

According to Zafirakou (2018) and Dewey (2013), educational application may help students to have great learning experience and that theory is more relevant to current study because the current study states that the mobile application will provide the students with some knowledge on how the mobile academic application can affect their academic performance. It will give students the ideas regarding the advantages and disadvantages of using mobile academic applications and how these applications can help them in terms of studying.

According to Sharples, Taylor and Vavoula (2007) mobile phones can also improve the learning of the students as students can access their mobile phones anytime and anywhere to study.

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Conceptual Framework

Fig.1 Relationship between Independent Variable and Dependent Variable.

The independent variable is the positive effects of educational mobile application because it can be the reason to change the performance of Grade 11 student in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela.

The dependent variable is the academic performance of Grade 11 students that can be changed by the use of educational mobile application.

Living in generation of technologies with an innovation in different aspects and one of these is the learning, the way of educating by the mobile application. Some mobile applications are educational that can affect the academic performance of the students.

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Statement of the Problem

The main concern of this present study is to create an awareness on Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela upon using educational mobile applications.

In line with this objective, stated below are the problems that will be addressed throughout the study:

1. What are the positive effects of the usage of various educational mobile applications to the academic performance of the Grade 11 students?
2. What are the factors that affects the academic performance of Grade 11 students related to the Educational Mobile Applications?

Significance of the Study

The importance of this present study will provide some knowledge to students on how the mobile academic applications can affect their academic performance. It will give the students an idea of the advantages on using mobile academic applications and how the mobile academic applications can help them in terms of studying.

The importance of this present study can provide data that will be a guide to the teachers and let them know how the academic applications can help their students in study purpose. Also, teachers would be able to understand why their students need to use the academic applications inside their classroom. The findings will also help them find out what applications can help them on their way of teaching.

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The beneficiaries of this present study are the parents. Parents have the authority to know the effects of using educational applications and understand how these applications can help their children and how it can affect the academic performance of their children. The findings would help the parents to know the action or performances of their children in school using and without using some mobile academic applications.

In conclusion, the proposed study will benefit and help the future researchers as their guide. This study can also be used in development of their study.

Scope and Limitation

This study aims to know the positive effects of using educational mobile applications and factors affects educational mobile applications to the academic performance of the Grade 11 students of St. Gregory College of Valenzuela, School Year 2019-2020. This research will be done through a survey research and interview. The Grade 11 students and teacher in Senior High School in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela will represent as population. This study is limited to present four educational mobile applications (Merriam Webster, Power Point, Word Document and Google) to help the Grade 11 students with academic performance.

In this study, researchers will present four limited educational mobile applications namely; Merriam Webster, Power Point, Word Document and Google to the Grade 11 students to know which among of these applications participants always use and which application can help them improve their academic performance in school.

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Definition of Terms

E-Learning - a complex system involving the student experience of learning, teachers' strategies, teachers' planning and thinking, and the teaching/learning context. (Alexander, 2001)

M-Learning – short for mobile learning, it offer methods which decrease the limitations of traditional education. (Georgieva, Georgieva & Smrikarov, 2004)

Statistical method – involved in carrying out a study include planning, designing, collecting data, analysis, drawing meaningful interpretation and reporting of the research findings. (Anaesth, 2016)

Strategy – A plan of action designed to achieve a long-term or overall aim. (Oxford Dictionary, 2019)

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Chapter II

RELATED REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Local Literature

Fototana and Rante (2017), states that application programmers, design, create, and test the software programs for business applications, desktop operating system, networking, websites, and video games. In the last few years, technology has changed the way of teaching and learning. Even the learning and teaching process has been changed innovated. Studies nowadays are mostly using this type of technology which are the educational mobile applications that can be the easy way to find or to know something in a short period of time. Now, education is no more restricted to lectures, talks and physical objects, as digitization has overcome this pattern of study.

Additionally, there are various educational mobile applications available in the market but selecting the right one can change their mindset at the process of learning. Educational applications are making things easier to understand and making learning fun to the core.

Local Studies

Vazquez (2014), stated that mobile applications has been developed through two perspectives; the first being through a descriptive methodology in which the current

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researcher has detailed the creation process of an application. The second perspective being through a quantitative methodology in which students' perceptions regarding the capabilities of smartphones and apps for improving learning processes in university subjects were assessed.

Vazquez (2014), concluded that the use of applications developed specifically for following university subjects is highly valued by students as a new format which both supports and enhances learning practices while also providing not only further opportunities to establish connections and relations with their subjects, but also fostering collaborative work among students and professors. In this generation using gadgets is very trend and one of the part of individual's life. Using cellphone is very popular and have many benefits according to usage like it can be used for communication, gathering data, and also for better performance to school and it is according to the applications that will be used. When it comes on school performance, there's an app that can help the students to make the study easier. It can also affect the performance of the students in the academic purposes. In addition, applications can be used to improve learning and participation of the students and it can improve their self-confidence. To conclude that, students valued the apps as their learning materials that can help to improve their studies and to improve learning of the student.

As Bandalaria (2005), states on her study entitled *Education for All Through the Mobile Phone: The University of the Philippines Open University Experience* "From time to time, people would want answers to some common questions and would seek

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practical knowledge and bits and pieces of information pertaining to health, for instance, language, etc. Ideally, one would go to a bookstore to buy a book on the topic, or search the Internet. A book may prove to be expensive and going to a bookstore requires time which sometimes busy people could not find. Again, searching the Internet would mean knowledge and skills on the use of the hardware and the software and may cost at least Php 15 per hour. Providing access to these practical information through the cellular phone upon demand would prove to be not only convenient but cheaper as well to the individual."

The author said that from time to time, people want answers to some common questions. Not everyone would want to have a formal degree or to be a professional to just answer common questions, they just want a practical knowledge to help them with their everyday concerns. Nowadays we don't really have to go to libraries that will take a lot of time, it will take time to find the book, and to get a particular topic needed. Buying a book to get information is very costly, just like going to internet cafes that will probably cost from Php 15 to Php 30 per hour. Information that the users need are just on the tip of their fingers, with the help of the technologies of our time. Most of people nowadays can afford to buy a mobile phone that can help them to provide the information that they need. No proper training is required to use those kind of technology, and technologies helps people to make their life easier, just how a mobile phone can help to get the information that people need.

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A study of Alday and Pascual (2012), states that E-teaching is a method that uses E-learning to educate the students. They also stated that "The teachers of the graduate school are highly competent with regards to computer skills necessary for E-teaching. They have significant positive attitudes toward E-teaching and E-learning. Furthermore, they demonstrated interest and enthusiasm in indulging into various E-teaching strategies." The proponents aim to promote a concept of e-learning or mobile learning to the future users of the proposed system. As imposed on the study the educators also agreed on the significant effects of E-learning that will maximize the teaching potentials for teachers as well as learning potentials of the students.

Mobile learning nowadays have such a big factor around the globe for those students wanting to learn more not only in school, but also outside of the school. Mobile learning provides all the information a student needs, in order to finish paper works or and assignments. There are private schools in the Philippines that are already using tablets for schoolwork. This is good news, but unfortunately, most of these tablets are only used for reading e-books and most probably used by students for gaming. There are yet many things that can be done in order to maximize the school and the parents' investment on a phone tablet. This is the reason why researchers would like to introduce M-Learning.

In addition, people nowadays have many ways to gain more knowledge and have many ways to explore an easy way of learning. The easy way of gaining knowledge in this generation now is to have a gadget that will help and provide for gathering data

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or information to people and students. Gadgets like cellphone is one of the biggest factor that can help students to make the study easy. Mobile phones have many uses that can help the students like using an application that will improve students learning and performance. Mobile learnings also can help students in various ways like using a specific application to improve their studying. Of course mobile learnings in this generation is for the students now, as a new material that can help them study. Many schools in the Philippines allows the students to use mobile phone because of its impact and purposes especially, help them to study easily.

The Philippines is way behind when it comes to E-learning and M-Learning. Just an example, E-learning, which found itself into the mainstream sometime early 2000s, is just making its way into Philippine learning circles today. In other parts of the world, E-Learning is becoming a little outdated as more and more people are switching from the traditional desktops to tablets or phablets (phone + tablet); thus making M-Learning is the next big thing. The proponents see that there are a lot of factors that can contribute to the slow emergence of E-Learning and M-Learning in the country, example of these are the availability and high cost of internet, accessibility to computers, and cost of owning a computer (Alday, & Pascual, 2012).

This study concludes that students who use mobile devices as a guide in their study will help them have a higher frequency to gain knowledge, to improve student's performance and to improve their social skills and social performance and this study

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wants to say that schools should allow the students to use technologies to have better learning experience.

Foreign Literature

Integrating e-learning technologies can cause for an improvement and changes on education system (Archer, Garrison & Anderson, 1999) this may possess advantages to both teachers and students.

According to Roy (2017), there are advantages of using mobile applications in education, he states, "In these changing times, students are more driven towards using a mobile phone for every purpose. A smartphone they call it. The world is at the fingertips and a student can get access to any information from anywhere. This reduces the chance of visiting a library and searching for the data. A mobile phone hence can be used for a number of such purposes. What makes the information easily available is mobile applications. Every mobile application has a unique feature which offers its own set of services.

Learning is a continuous process and the focus has now completely shifted to E-Learning. Due to the mobile phones and the various feature-oriented applications, students can learn at their pace and take their time at understanding things, as everything is just a click away.

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As Roy said, informations are already on the tip of our fingers. Our life have been more easy becuase of the help of technologies nowadays. Reducing the chances that people to go to libraries.

When it comes to education, mobile phones don't only help the students to find the information that they need, but there are certain mobile applications that has a certain purpose. The different features of every applications can help students in diffirent aspects to make their life easier.

Roy also gave 5 advantages using mobile applications in room and 2 of these can affect the performance of the students.

1. New Learning Methods

“The introduction of applications in the edcuation sector has led to the introduction of new learning methods. There are fun games available on mobile applications that indulge the students into a healthy thought process and help them understand things from a different perspective.” Using mobile applications in education introduce new way of learning to students. Learning can be more fun now because of the game features of mobile applications that can also help students to learn new things and look at things in a different perspective. Mobile applications nowadays has a dual purpose, programmers make make it more fun to study because of the features added in the educational applications.

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2. eBooks And Online Study

“These days, students are generally very fond of online studying. This is where library applications and book search applications come into the picture. These applications make it easy for the students to search the appropriate study material in the mobile application. It keeps them closer to the study material and helps them in segregating their studying materials over the web.” Nowadays, going to libraries are not necessary anymore because we can access the information that we need through our mobile phones. There are mobile applications like library applications or book search application that make it easy to get the study material that the students need.

According to study of Teodorescu (2015), the use of mobile language application can offer different content material adjusted to the student’s. The students using mobile application also seem to be more refreshing to learn both in formal and informal settings, especially if timely feedback on students’ performance is provided. Furthermore, students also show less anxiety.

According to the studies of Klimova (2019), mobile academics applications can help students to be more productive in class participation and enhance their self confidence. Nowadays, some students becomes more stress because of difficulty in academic study, in that way mobile academic applications are more helpful to the students to exhibit less stress and anxiety because mobile academic apps helps students to study easily. In addition, as the study of Klimova (2019) revealed that the students who use the mobile application in their learning have significantly higher

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learning outcomes than students who do not use academic application. Mobile academic application can help students to gain learnings easily and to have better performance than the students didn't use mobile academic application.

Through cognitive process, learners are allowed to explore more, apply the gathered ideas and resources from experiences, students can show and or present what they have learned through cognition, which may also apply for reflection or doing students' homework. According to the findings, the advantages of E-learning includes an ability to deliver the learnings immediately through academic offline application or through online resources, providing great approach through interaction with of any devices, tends to reciprocity, adaptability and concession in having an internet access, effortless by just typing-and-clicking a particular information and does not require proper training for the students.

According to Loveless (2019), there is evidence that the use of educational apps does help children learn. For example, education researcher Maya Lopuch found that elementary and middle school students who used various iPad apps as part of their learning curriculum improved their performance on a national assessment of Common Core domains. Students raised their performance nine percentage points, from the 51st to the 60th percentile after using iPads for just three months. University of Southern California professor Michelle Riconscente found that fifth graders' test scores improved just over 15 percent, compared with a control group, after playing a fractions game app for 20 minutes each day over a five-day period. Finally, Houghton

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Mifflin conducted a study measuring the effectiveness of using an app to help learn algebra in middle schoolers. They found that 20 percent more students scored 'Proficient' or 'Advanced' in understanding algebra using the app rather than a textbook. In addition using mobile educational apps in study is more efficient to boost the self-esteem of the students and can boost the learnings of the students. Mobile educational apps can motivate students to study proficiency and gain more knowledge. It is effective in the way of studying to improve their performance. It can also advance the student in academic purposes and to have high probability to students' academic success.

Foreign Studies

Basham, Marino, Rice and Xie (2010), asserted that mobile technologies hold a great deal of potential for all learners but especially those with disabilities. These technologies provide learners with dynamic, lightweight, portable, virtual toolboxes for various learning needs. In this article, we systematically reviewed current studies to find the overall research trends regarding the research purposes, methodologies, learning outcomes, academic content areas, and the interplay of demographic variables and the effectiveness of M-learning. The findings and implications of this review provide M-learning designers, educators, and researchers with valuable references and suggestions regarding the use of M-learning in designing and the implementation of lifelong learning plans for learners with disabilities. Both practice and research should consider the instructional design of M-learning with a focus on learner needs

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and other environmental context factors, instead of only on mobile tools themselves. The various learner interactions that take place in an M-learning experience shape the associated outcomes. These interactions should be considered when designing, implementing, and researching these experiences. The rapid pace of development and adoption of M-learning devices intensify the need for developers, educators, researchers, and the learners themselves to better understand how to effectively make use of M-Learning.

According to Basham, Marino, Rice, and Xie (2010), mobile technologies comes with a great potential of being learning medium. As technologies are dynamic, light-weight and portable which gives an owner of some technology with benefits. Those people with disabilities are most benefited when it comes to having a personal mobile phone. In addition to the researcher's idea mobile phones with educational mobile application comes with many good effects especially in academic purposes.

Learning capabilities of people with disabilities are said to be less than to the normal one. According to the researcher's findings, using mobile technology provides plans for learning plans for learner's disabilities. According to the findings, the development of mobile technologies greatly benefits the disabled people.

According to Sharples, Taylor and Vavoula (2005), learners can get regular-development in mobile learning, where learners develops their knowledge continually. With the use of portable technologies, students can gather ideas and many knowledge in a specific location. The students also can merge their knowledge gained

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earlier from different academic context like books and ideas to their new learnings through strategies that provides lifetime of learning by the means of mobile technology. According to the researcher's findings students also learned from topic to topic though mobile learning as medium, that helps them accomplish their personal learning plan.

Synthesis

The era nowadays compared to the last generations is more technological as there are many advancements in mobile phones, computer and other gadgets. Programmers used their skills to perform not only in advancements of technologies but also for educational purposes as Fototana and Rante (2017), states. Bandalaria (2005), also said that people wants to answer questions in more practical way like using mobile and cellular phones as it is in demand now around the globe. Cellular phones can get any information anywhere. As a result, the programmers focus now more in programming E-learning or mobile educational applications. In addition to what Roy (2017), states students nowadays can just click their phones to provide knowledge. In accordance to what students can have, there are five new benefits can someone have when using mobile phone especially mobile educational application. The new learning method, enhance parent teacher communication, e-books and online studies, miscellaneous function and decrease communication gap between students and Institution.

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Mobile learning really benefits the user. In accordance to the studies of Basham, Marino, Rise and Xie (2010), the people most benefited from using mobile phones as learning medium are those who are persons with disabilities as mobile phones are portable and easy to use. In addition, as Sharples, Taylor and Vavoula (2005), said that mobile phones are useful as it provides information more added to the gained knowledge in what books have.

In comparison to what all the authors said, technology especially mobile phones are more effective and more beneficial than someone can expect. Mobile educational applications are great learning medium for most of the people, person with disabilities and students in academic and learning purposes.

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Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers used the Quantitative Research wherein "emphasize objective measurements and the statistical, mathematical, or numerical analysis of data" (Babbie, 2010). The term *emphasize* means "giving special importance" and the term *statistical* means using mathematical methods in which all the researchers agreed into it for the group discussion conducted. The researchers used the descriptive research that suits for the study as it aimed to know the effects of the educational mobile applications to the academic performance of Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela wherein this study "focuses on gathering numerical data and generalizing it across groups of people or to explain a particular phenomenon" (Babbie, 2010). The researchers will use the survey research and interview to the respondents to identify the effects of educational mobile applications in academic performance of Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela and for the validity and reliability of the study.

Research Locale

St. Gregory College of Valenzuela is one of the private school in Valenzuela established on year 2007. Researchers chose the St. Gregory College of Valenzuela as

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the locale area of the study because this institution is available and as well the researchers are also from here. The researchers chose the Grade 11 students, who are suitable for the study because they encounter new subjects that are different from the Junior High School. And the teachers that allows students to use the mobile phones in academic purposes.

Instrumentation

The researchers will use survey questionnaire and interview to identify the effects of educational mobile applications in the academic performance of the Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela. Survey questionnaire will be used because it contains a set of questions that will be answered based on the experienced of the respondents. And also survey questionnaire is improving the number of accuracy of responses to the study that needed by the researchers. The respondents for the interview are the five (5) Senior high school teacher. Researchers used both subject completed and researcher completed. In subject completed is the questionnaire because score of the respondents can interpreted by the researchers while in researcher completed is the interview. Additionally each questionnaire asks for the identification of the respondents (optional), it has also a directions to be followed as a guide. Confidentiality of the gathered data of the respondents were assured.

Sampling and Sampling Techniques

The sampling technique used by the researchers is the probability sampling, where the population are the Grade 11 students and teachers in St. Gregory College

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of Valenzuela School Year 2019-2020. By the used of simple random sampling, researchers decided to choose the participants ten (10) students in every section and five (5) random Senior High School Teachers. St. Gregory College of Valenzuela has four (4) strand with five (5) section namely: Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), General Academic Strand (GAS I), (GAS II) and Accountancy and Business Management (ABM) with the total of fifty (50) participants. The researchers used the survey research and interview, which contains a number of questions that are answerable by the experienced of the respondents. The questions established by the researchers are interconnected to each other to assure that the study has reliability and validity.

Data Gathering Procedure

*Fig 2.*The process of research.

In gathering data the researchers will conduct a survey research by the used of survey questionnaires that will be answered by the respondents, and interview for validation on the gather data. Upon having the approval researchers will establish set

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of question. Study will be conducted by the use of survey research to the Grade 11 students in every strand with ten (10) participants with the total of fifty (50) respondents and five (5) teachers in Senior High School in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela.

The researchers will use the conduct statistical treatment wherein "is a catch all term which means to apply any statistical method in data" (Glen, 2019). And one of the subcategories is data analysis wherein "a process used by researchers for reducing data to a story and interpreting it to derive insights" (Surendran, 2019). In the term statistical method means "interpretation of data".

After the study has been conducted by the use of survey research and interview the identification of the respondents will be identified and the confidentiality will be assured and secured. The researchers will get the answers of the respondents based on their own experience. After the data was collected it will be analyzed with the use of tables, researchers can explain clearly and understand furthermore about the study from the data that has been collected using survey questionnaires, as a result, the researchers can identify the positive effects of educational mobile applications in Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela.

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Chapter IV

ANALYSIS, DISCUSSION AND PRESENTATION OF DATA

This chapter presents the results and findings of the study.

The researchers aim to know what are positive effects and factors affect using Educational Mobile Applications or (EMA). The researchers formulate questions "What is the positive effects/factors that affect using Educational Mobile Applications?" the choices given is from the review related literatures or RRL of the study that researchers gathered. And all the choices gathered are all validated by the five (5) Senior High Teacher and all of them are strongly agreed.

1. What are the positive effects of usage of various educational mobile applications?

Table 1 The frequency of positive effects of EMA

POSSITIVE EFFECTS	ABM	STEM	HUMSS	GAS1	GAS2	FREQUENCY
New Learning Material	3	5	1	3	1	13
Easier Time Management	1	2	0	2	4	9
Easier To Gather Data And Information	6	2	8	4	4	24

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Brings An Active Performance Participation	0	0	0	1	1	2
Online Studying	0	1	1	0	0	2

The table 1, shows the frequency of the positive effects. And the positive effects that got the highest frequency of 24 is the "Easier to gather data and information" as the students mostly used EMA because this is only way of gathering data and information in easier period of time. Likewise as (Albay & Pascual 2012), (Bandalaria 2008), (Klimova 2019), and (Vasquez 2014), stated in general that EMA is one of the instrument to have an easy way to gather data and information especially by the students.

The other four (4) positive effects are the following: (1) new learning material (Albay & Pascual 2012) and (Vasquez 2014) that got 13 (2) easier time management (Bandalaria 2008) that got 9 and both (3) bring an active performance participation (Alabay & Pascual 2012), (Klimova 2019) and (Loveless 2019) and (4) online study (Roy 2017) that got 2.

2. What are the factors that affect the academic performance of the related to the Educational Mobile Applications?

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Table 2 The Frequency of the Factors that Affect Academic Performance

FACTORS	ABM	STEM	HUMSS	GAS1	GAS2	FREQUENCY
Enhance Learning Materials	2	4	1	5	2	14
Provide All The Info Student's Need	3	4	2	4	2	15
Easier Studying Method	4	1	6	1	5	17
New Learning Practices	1	1	1	0	1	4

The table 2, above shows the frequency of the factors that affects the academic performance. And the factor that got the highest frequency of 17 is the Easier Studying Method (Roy 2017), said that EMA in modern society introduce new learning method to make it more fun as it have features for students.

The other three (3) factors that affect academic performance are the following: (1) Provide all the information the student need (Albay & Pascual 2012), (Bandalaria 2008), and (Vasquez 2014) that got a frequency of 15, (2) Enhance learning material (Vasquez 2014) that got a frequency of 14 and (2) New learning practices (Klimova 2019) and (Sharples, Taylor & Vavoula 2007) that got a frequency of 4.

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In addition for the study, most common EMA among the four (4) limited EMA (Google, Merriam Webster, Word Documents, and PowerPoint). The frequency break down shown in graph below.

Table 3 The Frequency of EMA

	GOOGLE	MERRIAM WEDSTER	WORD DOCU- MENT	POWERPOINT
ABM	9	1	0	0
STEM	9	1	0	0
HUMSS	9	0	0	1
GAS1	8	0	2	0
GAS2	9	0	0	1
FREQUENCY:	44	2	2	2

The table 3, shows that Google is mostly EMA used by the Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela that got the highest frequency of 44 followed by the Word Documents, Merriam Webster and PowerPoint that got a total of 2.

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Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary of the study pointing out the important findings with its conclusions and recommendations.

Summary

This study aimed to create an awareness on Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela upon using Educational Mobile Applications (EMA).

Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What are the positive effects of the usage of Educational Mobile Applications?
2. What are the factors that affect the academic performance related to the Educational Mobile Applications?

This study made used quantitative research, with the research instrument of gathering data are survey questionnaire and interview for the validation. The researchers conducted a survey with survey questionnaires for the fifty (50) students in Grade 11 and interview for the five (5) Senior High Teachers for the validation from St. Gregory College of Valenzuela. The researchers analyzed the data using statistical treatment and table for the tally, to identify the effects of educational mobile applications to the academic performance of Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela.

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The following synthesizes the results and the findings of the study:

1. What are the positive effects of usage of various educational mobile applications?

The positive effects of educational mobile application are the following; (1) New Learning Material, (2) Easier Time Management, (3) Easier to gather data and information (4) Bring an active performance, and (5) Online Study. The five positive effects of educational applications are gather from the review related of literature and validated by the five Senior High School Teacher and answered by the Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela. Among to the five positive effects the "Easier to gather data and information" got the highest frequency that they can access and get the information they need in easier way compared if they use other references.

Followed by New Learning Material, Easier Time Management, Bring an active Performance Participation and Online Study. They use Educational mobile applications or (EMA) because it is a New Learning Material for their studies and when use EMA they can have an Easier Time Management they can manage they their respected time as they use EMA. By that EMA bring an active performance participation during their discussion and lastly EMA is an Online Study as mostly of students are now using the technology and they are aware for this applications.

2. What are the factors that affect the academic performance of the related to the Educational Mobile Applications?

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The four (4) factors affect the academic performance of the students related to the educational mobile applications are gathered from the review related to literature and validated by the five (5) Senior High School Teachers and answered by the Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela. Among the four (4) factors that affect “Easier Studying Method” got the highest frequency, Grade 11 students use EMA because it is a new studying method for them and it can help from their studies and besides EMA also can provide all the information that they need. As EMA is a new studying method it also enhances the learning material and learning practices that students need in their daily lives as well in their respective studies.

Conclusion

Upon the gathered data by the researchers, the positive effects of educational mobile applications are the following; (1) New Learning Material (Albay and Pascual 2012) and (Vasquez 2014), (2) Easier Time Management (Bandalaria 2008), (3) Easier to gather data and information (Albay & Pascual 2012), (Bandalaria 2008), (Klimova 2019), and (Vasquez 2014), (4) Bring an active performance participation (Alabay & Pascual 2012), (Klimova 2019) and (Loveless 2019), and (5) Online Study (Roy 2017). And the factors that affect the academic performance related to educational mobile applications are the following; (1) Enhance learning material (Vasquez 2014), (2) Provide all the information the student needs (Albay & Pascual 2012), (Bandalaria 2008), and (Vasquez 2014), (3) Easier Studying Method (Roy 2017), and (4) New learning practices (Klimova 2019) and (Sharples, Taylor & Vavoula 2007). All

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the listed positive effects and factors affect the academic performance of the students related to the Educational Mobile Applications are verified and strongly agreed by the interviewees. And all the positive effects and factors affects got frequency from the Grade 11 students as the respondents.

And in addition, the most Educational Mobile Application that Grade 11 students usually used is the Google which got the highest frequency among the four (4) limited Educational Mobile Applications introduced by the researcher to the respondents.

Therefore the researchers conclude that Educational Mobile Applications (EMA) has a relationship to the students because it has a positive effects towards the students in their academic performance in school. Like it can be an easy way to gather information and data and they can save more time. Hence, it is a new learning material and online study that students need and by this students are more active in performance and their participation to the class.

And furthermore, Educational Mobile Applications are created to help the students in their studies (Fototana and Rante 2017) or also known as E-learning or M-Learning as Albay and Pascual (2012), it is promoted to maximize the teaching potential and as well learnings of the students.

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Recommendations

Upon having the research study, researchers aim to know the effects of educational mobile applications to the academic performance of the Grade 11 students in St. Gregory College of Valenzuela. On the other hand, researchers recommend to the people who can read the research study and to the future researchers are specified by the following;

1. Electronic Learning or E-Learning and Mobile Learning or M-Learning can be the new learning and teaching material for both teachers and students as Albay and Pascual (2012).
2. Educational mobile applications can be a new learning material for the students.
3. This paper is a good source of information, researchers recommends to read it comprehensively to understand more about effects of educational mobile applications to the academic performance of the students.
4. The upcoming researchers can apply correlation study on the effects of educational mobile applications to academic performance of the students.
5. Future researchers can also focuses on specific effect of educational mobile applications on the students.

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APPENDIX A SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE

Name (optional): _____ Strand: _____

I: Check your answer.

II: Check your answer.

Educational Mobile Application or (EMA)

	Always	often	Some times	Never
1. I use Educational Mobile Applications.				
2. I use EMA in my studies.				
3. Most EMA can help me in my academic performance.				
4. Some of our teachers allow us to use phones for academic purposes.				
5. I get the information I need using EMA.				

6. What is the purpose of your phone?

- Communication Searching
 Entertainment Social Media
 Documentation Other: Specify _____

7. Which of the following EMA do you use?

- Google Word document
 Merriam Power Point
 Other: Specify _____

8. What do you think is the positive effects of the Educational Mobile Application?

- New learning material
 Easier time management
 Easier to gather data and information
 Brings an active performance participation
 Online study
 Other: Specify _____

9. What factor do you think affect the academic performance of the students related to Educational Mobile Application?

- Enhance learning practices
 Provide all the information a student need
 Easier studying method
 New Learning Practices
 Other: Specify _____

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APPENDIX B

INTERVIEW

- a. Do you allow your students to use educational mobile applications or (EMA) for educational purposes or even during discussion?
- b. Do you see EMA as new learning materials for the students?
- c. Does EMA promote easier time management for the students?
- d. Does EMA can create easier gathering data and information?
- e. Can EMA brings an active performance participation on students?
- f. Does online studying is one of the positive effect of EMA?
- g. Does EMA can enhance learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?
- h. Does EMA can provide all the information that students need?
- i. Does EMA can create easier studying method?
- j. Does EMA can creates new learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

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APPENDIX C

TRANSCRIPT OF INTERVIEW

Interviewer: Student

Interviewee: Mr. Micheal Papiona from SHS Teacher (Grade 11)

(Start of interview)

Interviewer: Do you allow your students to use educational mobile applications or (EMA) for educational purposes or even during discussion?

Interviewee: Yes, especially when it comes to grammar kasi yung mga bata mahina yan pagdating sa comprehension at may mga words na hindi alam which is yung vocabulary nila mababa ang level.

Interviewer: Do you see EMA as new learning materials for the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA promote easier time management for the students?

Interviewee: Yes, mas mapapabagal yung pag gamit ng oras sa pagsesearch.

Interviewer: Does EMA can create easier gathering data and information?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Can EMA brings an active performance participation on students?

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Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does online studying is one of the positive effect of EMA?

Interviewee: No

Interviewer: Does EMA can enhance learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

Interviewee: Yes, nai-improve rin kase yung logical thinking.

Interviewer: Does EMA can provide all the information that students need?

Interviewee: Hindi lahat

Interviewer: Does EMA can create easier studying method?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can creates new learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewee: Ms. Moisesa N. Gutierrez from SHS Teacher (Grade 11)

(Start of interview)

Interviewer: Do you allow your students to use educational mobile applications or (EMA) for educational purposes or even during discussion?

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Interviewee: No, and depende rin sa school kung may magagamit na devices like computers pag hindi edi mobile phones.

Interviewer: Do you see EMA as e new learning materials for the students?

Interviewee: Yes of course, it is innovative devices, EMA are the applications student can use in their school days.

Interviewer: Does EMA promote easier time management for the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can create easier gathering data and information?

Interviewee: Yes, mas mapapabilis pag gawa ng estudyante.

Interviewer: Can EMA brings an active performance participation on students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does online studying is one of the positive effect of EMA?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can enhance learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can provide all the information that students need?

Interviewee: Hindi lahat, pero karamihan oo.

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Interviewer: Does EMA can create easier studying method?

Interviewee: Maybe

Interviewer: Does EMA can creates new learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewee: Mr. Julius Ramos from SHS Teacher (Grade 11)

(Start of interview)

Interviewer: Do you allow your students to use educational mobile applications or (EMA) for educational purposes or even during discussion?

Interviewee: Yes,

Interviewer: Do you see EMA as new learning materials for the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA promote easier time management for the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can create easier gathering data and information?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Can EMA brings an active performance participation on students?

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Interviewee: Not really

Interviewer: Does online studying is one of the positive effect of EMA?

Interviewee: Yes, but there are distractions like social media.

Interviewer: Does EMA can enhance learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

Interviewee: Maybe

Interviewer: Does EMA can provide all the information that students need?

Interviewee: Maybe, because EMA can only provide some knowledge.

Interviewer: Does EMA can create easier studying method?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can creates new learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewee: Mr. Jomar Peralta from SHS Teacher (Grade 11)

(Start of interview)

Interviewer: Do you allow your students to use educational mobile applications or (EMA) for educational purposes or even during discussion?

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Interviewee: Hindi ko sya pinapagamit sa oras ng discussion, sa assignments or project lang.

Interviewer: Do you see EMA as new learning materials for the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA promote easier time management for the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can create easier gathering data and information?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Can EMA brings an active performance participation on students?

Interviewee: No, kase nagiging tamad mga studyante.

Interviewer: Does online studying is one of the positive effect of EMA?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can enhance learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

Interviewee: Depende na iyon sa mga estudyante.

Interviewer: Does EMA can provide all the information that students need?

Interviewee: No, not all information kayang ibigay ng ema, madalas doon lang sa particular topic pero hindi sa buong aspect ng subjects.

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Interviewer: Does EMA can create easier studying method?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can creates new learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewee: Mr. Josie Hilario from SHS Teacher (Grade 12)

(Start of interview)

Interviewer: Do you allow your students to use educational mobile applications or (EMA) for educational purposes or even during discussion?

Interviewee: Oo

Interviewer: Do you see EMA as new learning materials for the students?

Interviewee: yes

Interviewer: Does EMA promote easier time management for the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can create easier gathering data and information?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Can EMA brings an active performance participation on students?

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Interviewee: Hindi lahat ng estudyante, yung iba tinatamad pa rin kahit nakakagamit naman ng EMA.

Interviewer: Does online studying is one of the positive effect of EMA?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can enhance learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can provide all the information that students need?

Interviewee: Maybe

Interviewer: Does EMA can create easier studying method?

Interviewee: Yes

Interviewer: Does EMA can creates new learning practices that can affect the academic performance of the students?

Interviewee: Yes